

THE BUILDING OF TRANSPORT DEMAND MODEL IN ROAD NETWORK OF ENTIRE KOSOVO**Valerie Bojku – Bibaj,***PhD candidate at Faculty of Technical Sciences,
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The main aim of this paper is to develop a model to planning and forecast the future road traffic and transport network in entire Kosovo. The inputs of this model consists the social and economic data, as: residents, employment, industries, recreation, administration, education, shopping, workplaces also the vehicle flow in all border points of Kosovo got from Kosovo Police, previous road-side survey (done by Multimodal Transport Strategy and Action Plan in 2011) and road improvement scenarios. Year 2016 is considered as the base year of the traffic forecast because it is the most recent year when yearly figures for input data are available. The calibration of the data is done by GEH test and finally is built the model using PTV Visum software in order to forecast the transport demand in the future in Kosovo.

Keywords: Road, forecast, future, modelling, PTV Visum, transport demand.

INTRODUCTION

A good transport system widens the opportunities to satisfy needs while a poor connected system restricts options and limits economic and social development [1].

This seminar paper describes the process and results of traffic forecast for entire Kosovo of road network. The forecast is necessary to find out if road network expansions shall meet the demands for transport. The outputs of this model are predicted road traffic volumes between origin and destination municipalities basing on attribute data of seven Kosovo regions.

Year 2016 is considered as the base year of the traffic forecast because it is the most recent year when yearly figures for input data are available, also it was in disposition the last road side survey in Kosovo which was undertaken in 2011.

The expansions of the road network is based in Sectorial Strategy of Multimodal Transport 2015-2025 by Infrastructure Ministry of Kosovo, it says, the first category include new motorways and one of them is "route 6" which include road section Prishtina – Hani i Elezit, (Arbën Xhaferi) to the border with Macedonia with the length of 65 km and the other one "route 7" which include road section Morinë – Prishtinë – Merdare, (Ibrahim Rugova) with the length of 118 km which connects to the border crossing of Vermica (border with Albania).

The objective of this Strategy is to link with pan – european corridors, thus, improvement, development and maintenance of transport infrastructure, which is integrated in pan-european corridors and it is in line with international standards.

While the objective of this paper is to know if new constructions and road improvement will meet the transport demand based on the growth of all variables forecasted in three scenarios, which is based on population, estimation and economic growth, then it has an effect on employment, so in this paper is planned to be the same road network for three scenarios but with three level of variables predicted.

Another objective is to provide security, sustainability and make it easier for transport planners and future decision makers to make decisions.

For forecasting in 2025, three scenarios are introduced, while the transport modelling is done by PTV Visum software.

GENERAL INFORMATION OF KOSOVO AND STUDY AREA

The territory of the Republic of Kosovo counts the surface of 10,905.25 km² with 1,798,506 inhabitants. It is situated in south-east Europe, limited with Albania on south-west part, Monte Negro at north-west, Serbia at north-east and with Macedonia at the south. The territory is situated at geographic latitude 41° 51' and 43° 16', and within geographic longitude 19° 59' and 21° 47'.

Fig. 1. Geographic position of Kosovo in relation to other countries [2]

In terms of regions, Kosovo has got seven regions, 38 municipalities and 1469 settlements. The regions of Kosovo are: Ferizaj, Gjakovë, Gjilan, Mitrovicë, Pejë, Prishtinë and Prizren, as presented in figure 2 and the development of the model has been done for Kosovo.

Fig. 2. The map of seven regions of Kosovo

THE MODELLING OF TRAVEL DEMAND IN ROAD NETWORK BASED ON ATTRIBUTES OF REGIONS

The modelling of travel demand in Kosovo is presented step by step in following text. 3.1

Step 1 - Zones, Roads and International connections

In total the state of Kosovo has seven regional zones. The following are the names of each traffic zone and the roads (figure 3):

The name of the zones are: Prishtine, Mitrovice, Peje, Gjakove, Prizren, Ferizaj and Gjilan.

Fig. 3. The zones and roads of Kosovo in 2016

In order to see the importance of the roads, in below figure apart from the nodes and zones are also presented the links with neighbouring countries, as:

- Tirana - direction Albania (Through Highway R7),
- Skopje - direction Macedonia (Through M2 or Highway which is under construction R6),

- Belgrade and Nis — direction Serbia (Through M2 and M25),
- Podgorica — direction Montenegro (Through M9).

In below figure are shown nodes and connections with neighbouring countries.

Fig. 4. The links with neighbouring countries

Step 2 - Inside and outside zones

In below figure are presented inside and outside zones (figure 5).

Fig. 5. Inside and outside zones

In order to do the modelling of Kosovo road network, it is necessary to present the attributes of regions. In below table are presented the data of each region.

Table 1

Employment and working place in region of Prishtina for the year 2016

Regions	2016						
	Prishtinë	Gjilan	Ferizaj	Prizren	Gjakovë	Pejë	Mitrovicë
Industries	31769	10287	11112	18075	16262	11278	14018
Shopping	16925	5481	5920	9632	8664	6010	7468
Services	11827	3830	4138	6731	6053	4201	5221
Administration	15385	4977	5378	8750	7867	5459	6784
Education	9973	3227	3487	5673	5102	3539	4399
Recreation	4987	1612	1743	2836	2551	1769	2202
Residents	484520	166210	179250	289400	260640	178330	225210
Workplaces	19130	3914	4064	7188	5570	1612	4785
Employment	90866	29414	31778	51697	46499	32256	40092

While the insertion of this data in PTV Visum for each zone are presented in table 2

Table 2

Attributes for Kosovo in PTV Visum- 2016 year

No	C Name	TypeNo	ADMINISTRATION	EDUCATION	EMPLOYMENT	FROM_ZONE	INDI
1	Prishtine	0	15385	9973	90866	0	
2	Mitrovicë	0	6784	4399	40092	0	
3	Pejë	0	5459	3539	32256	0	
4	Gjakovë	0	7867	5102	46499	0	
5	Prizren	0	8750	5673	51697	0	
6	Ferizaj	0	5378	3487	31778	0	
7	Gjilan	0	4977	3227	29414	0	
101	Merdare	0	0	0	0	349	
102	Mutrode	0	0	0	0	40	
103	Dheu i Bardhe	0	0	0	0	756	
104	Muqibabe	0	0	0	0	342	
105	Hani Elezit	0	0	0	0	957	
106	Gilboqice	0	0	0	0	223	
107	Verrice	0	0	0	0	1838	
108	Qafa e Prushit	0	0	0	0	201	
109	Qafa e Morines	0	0	0	0	265	
110	Kulla	0	0	0	0	162	
111	Delta 31 - Zubin Potok	0	0	0	0	159	
112	Gate 1 - Leposaviq	0	0	0	0	564	
INDUSTRIES	RECREATION	RESIDENTS	SERVICES	SHOOPING	TO_ZONE	WORKPLACES	
31769	4987	484520	11827	16925	0	19130	
14018	2202	225210	5221	7468	0	4785	
11278	1769	178330	4201	6010	0	1612	
16262	2551	260640	6053	8664	0	5570	
18075	2836	289400	6731	9632	0	7188	
11112	1743	179250	4138	5920	0	4064	
10287	1612	166210	3830	5481	0	3914	
0	0	0	0	0	708	0	
0	0	0	0	0	146	0	
0	0	0	0	0	1161	0	
0	0	0	0	0	441	0	
0	0	0	0	0	1029	0	
0	0	0	0	0	226	0	
0	0	0	0	0	2385	0	
0	0	0	0	0	204	0	
0	0	0	0	0	335	0	
0	0	0	0	0	199	0	
0	0	0	0	0	174	0	
0	0	0	0	0	651	0	

Source: Prepared in PTV VISUM

In the table 3 are presented all attributes

Table 3

All attributes presented

List (Attributes)

Number: 12	ObjTypeName	ObjID	AttID	ShortName	LongName	Value Type
1	Zones	ZONE	ADM	ADMINISTRATION	ADMINISTRATION	Integer
2	Zones	ZONE	EDU	EDUCATION	EDUCATION	Integer
3	Zones	ZONE	EMPL	EMPLOYMENT	EMPLOYMENT	Integer
4	Zones	ZONE	FROMZONE	FROM ZONE	FROM ZONE	Integer
5	Zones	ZONE	IND	INDUSTRIES	INDUSTRIES	Integer
6	Zones	ZONE	RECR	RECREATION	RECREATION	Integer
7	Zones	ZONE	RESIDENTS	RESIDENTS	RESIDENTS	Integer
8	Zones	ZONE	SER	SERVICES	SERVICES	Integer
9	Zones	ZONE	SH	SHOOPING	SHOOPING	Integer
10	Zones	ZONE	TOZONE	TO ZONE	TO ZONE	Integer
11	Zones	ZONE	WORKPL	WORKPLACES	WORKPLACES	Integer
12	Links	LINK	LC	link category	link category	Text

Source: Prepared in PTV VISUM

Step 3 - The traffic count in border points and the transit matrixes

The annual average day traffic in border points are taken from Kosovo Police and are presented in below table.

Table 4

The annual average Daly traffic in border points (AADT)

The border points		Year 2016	
		From zone	To zone
1	Merdare	708	349
2	Mutivodë	146	40
3	Dheu i Bardhe	1161	756
4	Muqibabë	441	342
5	Hani i Elezit	1029	957
6	Gllloboçicë	226	223
7	Vermicë	2385	1838
8	Qafa e Prushit	204	201
9	Qafa e Morinës	335	265
10	Kulla	199	162
11	Bërnjak	174	159
12	Jarinjë	651	564

Source: Kosovo Police

In order to establish the model of transport demand, outer zones play important role which also generate traffic. For their proper functioning it is necessary to create particular matrix for transiting traffic. Values on the intensity of traffic flow between outer zones for individual and goods transit traffic is shown in Table 5 and Table 6.

Those matrixes are prepared based on counting which is done by Ministry of Infrastructure in 2011, than is done the forecasting for 2016, based on the number of population and car ownership.

Table 5

Transit of passenger vehicle C-Transit (veh/h)

Code	O/D Matrix	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108	109	110	111	112
		Merdare	Mutivode	Dheu I Bardhe	Muqibabe	Hani Elezit	Gllloboqice	Vermice	Qafa e Prushit	Qafa e Morines	Kulla	Delta 31-Zubin Potok	Gate 1-Leposaviq
101	Merdare	0				4		2		2			
102	Mutivode		0										
103	Dheu I Bardhe	2		0			2	2					
104	Muqibabe				0			2					
105	Hani Elezit	2				0		5			22		2
106	Gllloboqice						0	2		2			
107	Vermice			4		5		0		4	2		
108	Qafa e Prushit							2	0				
109	Qafa e Morines							9		0			
110	Kulla										0		
111	Delta 31-Zubin Potok											0	
112	Gate 1-Leposaviq												0

Source: Prepared by author

Table 6

Transit of commercial vehicle TT Transit (veh/h)

Code	O/D Matrix	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108	109	110	111	112
		Merdare	Mutivode	Dheu I Bardhe	Muqibabe	Hani Elezit	Gllloboqice	Vermice	Qafa e Prushit	Qafa e Morines	Kulla	Delta 31-Zubin Potok	Gate 1-Leposaviq
101	Merdare	0				1							
102	Mutivode		0										
103	Dheu I Bardhe			0				1					
104	Muqibabe				0			2					
105	Hani Elezit					0		1			3		
106	Gllloboqice						0						
107	Vermice			1		1		0		1	1		
108	Qafa e Prushit								0				
109	Qafa e Morines							1		0			
110	Kulla										0		
111	Delta 31-Zubin Potok											0	
112	Gate 1-Leposaviq												0

Source: Prepared by author

In order to create the demand model it is necessary the trip generation, therefore the reasons of trips and factors which have impact in generating trips are presented in tables 7 and 8 than are inserted in PTV Visum.

Factors distribution for trips, six purposes regarding the parameters a, b and c are taken into account which are given in table 8 [4].

Table 7

Generating factor (productivity)

Purpose 6		Purpose 5		Purpose 4		Purpose 3		Purpose 2		Purpose 1		Attribute
attractive	productive											
0	0	0	0.06258	0	0.01819	0	0	0	0.00117	0	0	Residents
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00387	0	0	0	0.03001	Employment
0.07800	0.07800	0.09422	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	PW Industries
0.07800	0.07800	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00077	0	0	0	PW Education
0.15600	0.15600	0.09422	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	PW Recreation
0.15600	0.15600	0	0	0.79380	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	PW Shopping
0.15600	0.15600	0.18845	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	PW Administration
0.15600	0	0.18845	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	PW Service
0	0	0	0	0	0	0.03773	0	0	0	0.27939	0	Site workplaces
0	0.00858	0	0.00569	0	0.00909	0	0.00058	0	0.00029	0	0.01059	From Zone
0.00858	0	0.00471	0	0.01191	0	0.00566	0	0.00077	0	0.09861	0	To Zone

Source: Priracnik PTV VISION VISUM, TFB, Bitola, 2012 [3]

Factor distribution

Parameters Purpose	A	B	C
Purpose 1	4,3	1	-0,08
Purpose 2	3,8	1	-0,08
Purpose 3	3	1	-0,08
Purpose 4	3	1	-0,08
Purpose 5	4,2	1	-0,08
Purpose 6	3,8	1	-0,08

Source: By literature [3]

While, the attributes on productive and attractive factors for the group 1 inserted in PTV Visum, is shown in the following figure.

Fig. 6. Generation factor for Production and Attraction rate inserted in PTV Visum

Step 4 - The Modelling of transport demand with PTV Visum Software of base year 2016 (S0)

Taking into consideration all variables which are mentioned above, is done the modelling with PTV Visum for base year 2016, than the results from this situation are compared with the traffic flow automatic

count in some specific segments, also is made the verification with GEH test.

The situation of the road in that period of time was the same with now days, with the exception of Motorway Ferizaj Hani Elezit towards of the border of Macedonia. Therefore, in below figure 7 is presented the modelling.

Fig. 7. The Modelling of transport demand for base year 2016 – S0

The width of traffic (red colour) depends on its load. The highest traffic flow is recorded in Highway R7 then in segment direction to Mitrovica, than the segment toward Peja, etc.

Step 5 - The verification of results gained through the model compared to the real traffic flow in some specified road segments based on GEH - test

The GEH Statistic is a formula used in traffic engineering, traffic forecasting, and traffic modelling to compare two sets of traffic volumes.

Comparison results by traffic flow counting of 2011 year and modelling using PTV Visum is done by GEH test. GEH test can be calculated by Eq. (1), as follows:

$$GEH = \sqrt{\frac{2 \cdot (M - C)^2}{M + C}} \quad (1)$$

Where are:

M - Peak hour from current model (or new counts),

C - Peak hour from current of counting (or previous counts).

After completion of modelling for the situation of 2016 through PTV Visum software results are gained on the transport demand for entire road network of Kosovo.

The annual average traffic count of 2016

Code	Road	Place	AADT - 2016
C1	N2	Doganaj	10140
C2	R126	Vataj	1603
C3	N25.3	Sojevë	7784
C4	N25.3	Pasjan	3656
C5	N25.3	Raniluk	8457
C6	N25	Konjuh	11201
C7	N25.3	Carralevë	-
C8	N9	Sllatinë	42933
C9	N2	Babush	12728
C10	N25.3	Slivovë	8935
C11	N9	Grashticë	-
C12	N25	Vranidoll	12567
C13	N2	Millosevë	20251
C14	R101	Brobaniq	-
C15	N2	Koshtovë	4978
C16	N22.3	Simonida	-
C17	N9	Zahaq	10780
C18	R107	Dranoc	11486
C19	R107	Pirana	11384
C20	N25	Vlashnje	7788
C21	R115	Prizren	4541
C22	R110	Xërxë	8596
C23	N9.1	Qerim	4403
C24	R102	Trstenik	1051
C25	R101	Vitak	2164
C26	R129	Tuneli i Parë	1983

Source: Ministry of Infrastructure

While in the below figure are presented the locations of traffic automatic count.

Fig. 8. Traffic count location [6]

Presentation of comparison of these results according to automatic counters and modelling by PTV Visum with application of GEH formula test is shown in the following table.

Table 10

Comparison of results according to automatic counters, modelling by PTV Visum and GEH test

No.	The Points of traffic automatic count	The annual average daily traffic (AADT)	Modelling using PTV Visum	Difference in numbers	GEH test (%)
1	C15	4978	4940	38	0.539
2	C12	12567	12510	57	0.509
3	C10	8935	8610	325	3.469
4	C5	8457	8790	-333	3.585
5	C3	7784	7940	-156	1.759
6	C1	10140	10520	-380	3.738
7	C2	1603	1420	183	4.707
8	C20	7788	7820	-32	0.362
9	C23	4403	4320	83	1.256
10	C17	10780	10370	410	3.986
11	C18	11486	11780	-294	2.725
12	C9	12728	12290	438	3.916
13	C6	11201	11190	11	0.103

Source: Prepared by author

The comparison show that for all locations results are fulfilled under condition $< 5\%$, and by comparing results gained by traffic counting with results by modelling using PTV Visum we can conclude that they are under acceptable level. This ensure us not to do further research and that we may approve this model as final one which can be used as referring model to be used for forecasting of transport demand for the coming periods.

Step 6 - The Modelling of transport demand with PTV Visum Software of "Minimum Scenario" year 2025 (S1)

Because of the Sectorial Strategy and Multimodal Transport of Infrastructure Ministry of Kosovo is

planned until 2025, for three us scenarios is planned the same improvement of infrastructure, but are predicted the attributes data of each region of Kosovo in three levels:

- Minimal planning of increasing for 2025,
- Medium planning of increasing for 2025 and
- Maximum planning of increasing for 2025

With the attributes data of Minimal planning is done the modelling of transport demand for "Minimum Scenario" 2025.

Table 11

The minimal planning of increasing of Employment and working place in Kosovo for the year 2025

Regions	2025						
	Prishtinë	Gjilan	Ferizaj	Prizren	Gjakovë	Pejë	Mitrovicë
Industries	33104	10717	11577	18833	16945	11750	14608
Recreation	5199	1679	1816	2956	2659	1842	2295
Residents	459900	157700	170200	274800	247500	169300	213700
Services	12322	3989	4312	7013	6306	4377	5439
Shopping	17638	5711	6169	10036	9027	6263	7783
Administration	16029	5187	5606	9118	8198	5689	7068
Education	10157	3227	3496	5653	5052	3504	4356
Workplaces	19934	4078	4236	7491	5804	1680	4985
Employment	94449	30510	32976	53609	48187	33425	41549

Source: Prepared by author

To form OD matrix of base year is got in consideration car ownership. While based on population estimation, the population for Kosovo is dropping starting from 2016 and car ownership is growing, relevant indication to form O-D matrix 2016 is car ownership.

For this scenario is planned some changes compared with base year, as:

The road direction to Merdare the border with Serbia, which is planned to rehabilitation the magisterial

road, currently is with two lines and is planned to be with four lines also in this direction is planned to construction the Motorway and Linking of Gjilan region with Pristina with Motorway, towards the Dheu I Bardhe the border point with Serbia.

While, in below figure is presented the road network categorization and the modelling.

Fig. 9. The road categorization

Fig. 10. The modelling of Minimum Scenario – S1

Step 7 - The Modelling of travel demand with PTV Visum Software of “Medium Scenario” year 2025 (S2)

The comparison between scenarios based on level of service.

N0	Road segment	Category	LOS – (S0)	LOS – (S1)	LOS – (S2)	LOS – (S3)
1	C15	Nacional Road	C	C	C	D
2	C12	Nacional Road	F	A	A	A
2'	C12'	Motorway		A	A	A
3	C10	Nacional Road	E	A	A	A
3'	C10'	Motorway (Gjilan-Prishtine)	-	A	A	A
4	C5	Nacional Road	E	A	A	A
5	C3	Nacional Road	E	E	E	D
6	C1	Nacional Road	E	D	D	D
7	C2	Regional Road	B	A	A	A
8	C20	Nacional Road	E	E	E	E
9	C23	Nacional Road	C	C	C	C
10	C17	Nacional Road	A	A	A	A
11	C18	Regional Road	F	F	F	F
12	C9	Nacional Road	A	A	A	A
13	C6	Nacional Road	E	E	E	E
14	A	Motorway	A	C	C	C
15	B	Nacional Road	E	D	D	D

Source: Prepared by author.

CONCLUSION

In this study the variables that are get in consideration are some social economic data, traffic flow, road network, also are got seven of Kosovo regions which are considered as zones, as: Prishtine, Mitrovice, Peje, Gjakove, Prizren, Ferizaj and Gjilan and 12 outer zones (border points).

Because of in entire Kosovo the automatic counting in road network have worked unil 2016, the base year is got 2016, also is used the last available road side survey in Kosovo which was undertaken in 2011.

Because of the Sectorial Strategy and Multimodal Transport of Infrastructure Ministry of Kosovo is planned until 2025, for three us scenarios is planned the same improvement of infrastructure, but are predicted the attributes data of each region of Kosovo in three levels:

- minimal planning of increasing for 2025,
- medium planning of increasing for 2025 and
- maximum planning of increasing for 2025

The first scenario "Minimum Scenario" (S1) in which at the end of the period in 2025 is planned to constructio the Motorway towards Merdare and Dheu I Bardhe also the expansion of National road towards Podujeve from two in four lines, while the attributes (variables) are predicted for the end of 2025 with minimum increasing.

The second scenario "Medium Scenario" (S2) the gender of road network is the same as in scenario S1, but the attributes (variables) are predicted for the end of 2025 with medium increasing.

The third scenario "Maximum Scenario" (S3), also the gender of road network is the same as in scenario S1 and S2, but the attributes (variables) are predicted for the end of 2025 with maximum increasing.

To realize the modelling of road transport demand are necessary The traffic count in border points which are taken from Kosovo Police and the transit matrices for individual and goods transit traffic which are pre-

pared based on counting is done by Ministry of Infrastructure in 2011, than is done the forecasting for 2016, based on the number of population and car ownership.

Taking into consideration all variables which are mentioned above, is done the modelling with PTV Visum for base year 2016, than the results from this situation are compared with the traffic flow automatic count in some specific segments, also is made the verification with GEH test.

The comparison showed that for all locations results are fulfilled under condition $< 5\%$, and by comparing results gained by traffic counting with results by modelling using PTV Visum we can conclude that they are under acceptable level. This ensure us not to do further research and that we may approve this model as final one which can be used as referring model to be used for forecasting of transport demand for the coming periods.

After modelling is noticed that with construction the motorways towards Gjilan and Podujeva the level of service would be very good, but investment in direction of Podujeva (Merdare) in Nacional Road (C12) and in Motorway (C12') is unnecessary, because in this situation we have very big capacity, while as it can be seen in above table for three attribution increase scenarios, we have almost the same level of service, it means that at the end of 2025 the construction of the new roads mentioned above is not enough, because the road segments that have F, E and D service levels should be reviewed.

The model is built and will serve the policy makers to get appropriate decisions in the future for the entire Kosovo road network.

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